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Integrated Development of Marine and Fisheries of Sangihe Islands District, North Sulawesi, Indonesia

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ABSTRACT

The Integrated Development of Marine and Fisheries Areas (IDMFA) in the Sangihe Islands District is a regional-based marine and fisheries development concept. The development of IDMFA in the Sangihe Islands District is in the Santiago and Dagho regions. This selection was based on the fishery potential of the two regions. The progress of integrated marine and fishery areas (IDMFA) is based on the development of capture fisheries and aquaculture activities, including their marketing activities to improve community welfare.

Keywords: Integrated, Development, Marine and Fisheries, capture fisheries, Sangihe Island

INTRODUCTION

Sangihe Islands District is geographically located between 4°4'13" – 4°44'22" North Latitude and 125°9'28" – 125°56'57" East Longitude, located between Sulawesi Island and Mindanao Island (Republic of the Philippines) and is an integral part of North Sulawesi Province. The capital Tahuna has 142 nautical miles from Manado as the provincial capital. Overall, the area is 11,863.58 km² consisting of 736.98 km² of land (60% plains, 40% slopes and 11,126.61 km² of seas or 93.8%). This district has 105 small and tiny islands, of which 26 are inhabited and 79 are uninhabited, consisting of 15 sub-districts, 146 villages, and 22 sub-districts, where the territory is mostly made up of mountains and hilly land surrounded by oceans [1-10].

The Sangihe Islands District is bordered by the Talaud Islands District and the Philippine Mindanao Sea in the north, the Sulawesi Sea in the west, the Maluku Sea, and the Pacific Ocean east, and the Siau Islands in the south. The southernmost border island/water is Sanggaluhang Island, Tatoareng District. Meanwhile, the northernmost border islands/waters and islands located on the outermost line of the country's territory are Marore, Kawio, and Kawaluso Islands (Photo 1 to 27).

Directions for the Integrated Development for Marine and Fisheries Areas (IDMFA)

The Development of Integrated Marine and Fisheries Areas (IDMFA) in the Sangihe Islands District is located in the Santiago and Dagho regions.

The Santiago area is a former Bina Marga land that is no longer used, where on the inside of the site, there are still several buildings. The land belongs to the government, the Bina Marga Office, which is no longer actively used. There is a relatively sizeable non-built area, so there is no need for massive demolition of buildings. Some buildings are still standing and still allow reuse if the structure's condition is still feasible. The location is relatively close to the Tahuna urban area [2-10].

The Dagho area is a fishing port area developed previously, but its activities are now dead due to a lack of management and development of the area. Dagho has been defined in the Spatial plans Guidance of Sangihe Islands District as an area to be developed as a fishing port for the archipelago. The land belongs to the government and has been previously developed as a fishing port area. This area has several supporting facilities for fishing activities whose buildings are still suitable for use. The water conditions are relatively safe from waves, making it ideal for

landing fishing boats [10-15]. The growth/evolution of integrated marine and fishery areas (IDMFA) is based on the development of capture fisheries and aquaculture activities, including their marketing activities to improve community welfare.

Capture Fisheries

Based on data obtained from the Department of Marine Affairs and Fisheries of the Sangihe Islands District, catch production in 2020 was 8,488 tons consisting of 5,676 tons of small pelagic fish, 2,205 tons of large pelagic fish, and 421 tons of demersal fish. The dominant small pelagic fish is scad, while the sizeable pelagic fish is skipjack tuna, followed by yellowfin tuna and grouper demersal fish [3-7].

Based on the results of a survey and analysis of production and ship data published by DKP Sangihe, the estimated catch production in 2020 is 10,485 tons of fish (**Table 1**). The sustainable potential of fish resources in the Sangihe Islands District is 34,000 tons, so that the utilization rate of fish resources is 30.8%. Thus, fish resources can still be further optimized by 49.2% (16,715 tons). Optimizing the use of fish resources can be done by improving fishing technology and adding fishing vessels measuring 10 GT (4 units) and 30 GT (4 units), after optimizing the entire existing fishing fleet and providing knowledge related to fishing technology and fishing gear assistance, hand line for fishers measuring < 5 GT. This is based on the consideration that ships measuring < 5 GT are 93.6%, 5-10 GT are 6.2% and > 10 GT are 0.2% [1-8].

Table 1. Number of Fisher, Fishing Vessels and Catch Production in the Year 2020

No	Subdistrict	Fisher (Orang)	Fishing Vessels (Unit)	Production (Ton)
1	Tahuna Timur	490	195	494
2	Tahuna	216	345	2.369
3	Manganitu Selatan	2,543	202	282
4	Tabukan Utara	1,633	222	94
5	Tabukan Selatan Tengah	252	197	151
6	Tabukan Selatan	341	147	366
7	Marore	217	182	24
8	Tabukan Tengah	479	343	926
9	Kendahe	448	97	306
10	Tamako	677	328	2,104

No	Subdistrict	Fisher (Orang)	Fishing Vessels (Unit)	Production (Ton)
11	Manganitu	475	142	2,565
12	Nusa Tabukan	955	427	47
13	Tatoareng	772	311	254
14	Tahuna Barat	137	107	494
15	Tabukan Selatan Tenggara	34	26	9
Total		9,669	3,271	10,485

Source: Sangihe District in Number (2020)

The catch is marketed in fishermen's settlements, markets (various markets in the Sangihe Islands District), and Tahuna port and mediators because it is closer to their homes, has higher prices, and is more accessible. In the Sangihe Islands District waters, there are four seasons, namely the southern season occurring in August – October, the northern season occurring in October – February, the western season occurring in December – January, and the eastern season occurring in April – June. Based on interviews with fishers, it shows that the peak fishing season occurs in June-September. Fishers carry out fishing activities depending on weather conditions. In addition to the weather factor, religious holidays are also a reason not to go on sea [2-6, 10-14, 16-25].

The catches of pelagic fish are kite (malalugis), skipjack, yellowfin tuna, julung-julung (roa), and deho. Demersal fish catch includes *geropa* mice (rat grouper), *bobara* (yellowfish nail), jackfruit seeds, goats, and red snapper. In peak fishing season, the catch varies depending on the size of the vessel and fishing gear, from 50 kg to 500 kg in one trip. The profit-sharing system applied is an equal share (50% captains, 50% crew members), 75% captains, 25% crew members [2-6, 15-20, 25-30].

For fishers to get an increase in income, the catch can be collected in one place in addition to efficiency (reducing the cost of purchasing fuel) and facilitate data collection, which can then be sold between regions and for export (Photo 28 up to 102).

Aquaculture

Sangihe Islands District can develop marine aquaculture covering an area of 5,542.54 ha. These potentials include seaweed cultivation of around 4,549.86 ha, fish in KJA covering an area of 792.89 ha, pearl shellfish cultivation covering an area of 86.05 ha, and fish and sea cucumber cultivation in KJT covering an area of 113.75 ha.

The potential for the development of marine aquaculture in the Sangihe Islands District is generally bay waters, but some are open waters. Bay waters are semi-enclosed waters, so to maintain ecological balance in the development of aquaculture that can increase fertility

through increasing nitrogen into the waters, development is carried out based on the principle of trophic level-based mariculture. The development of one or a few carnivorous commodities causes an imbalance in the ecosystem because the production system of these commodities tends to produce waste (organic matter, ammonia, or nitrogen) which can no longer be tolerated by environmental forces [2-6, 20-25, 30-34].

At least five groups of commodities can be developed in potential water areas to develop marine aquaculture based on the consideration of the biological suitability (resources requirements) of the aquaculture biota mentioned above with the aquatic environment under study (ecophysiology of aquatic biota). These commodity groups are algae (seaweed), fish or finfish (grouper and other reef fish), crustaceans (lobster shrimp), mollusks (pearl shells and consumable shellfish), and echinoderms (sea cucumbers). Seaweed, grouper, lobster shrimp, pearl oysters, and sea cucumbers are marine aquaculture commodities with high economic value and are oriented towards international (export) markets [5-8, 10-25, 30-34].

From studying the marine environment (oceanography, water quality, and ecosystem) and determining the suitability of commodities, the study can also determine the recommended cultivation system. Several marine aquaculture systems that can be applied in the Sangihe Islands District include floating net cages (KJA) for grouper and lobster shrimp culture, tethered net cages (KJT) for sea cucumber and grouper cultivation, longline for seaweed and pearl oyster cultivation.

The carrying capacity approach of waters for aquaculture activities is carried out to support sustainable aquaculture activities. In addition, potential areas for mariculture development will overlap with other areas, such as protected areas with the status as a buffer zone for the core zone. For economic purposes, the regulations in force in the buffer zone in the protected area are of a limited nature. The zone can be used for economic activities not exceeding 20%. Based on these provisions, the potential area obtained from this study is corrected in advance following the applicable provisions in the buffer zone/limited use of protected areas.

Based on the description above, it is necessary to have a buffer zone and environmental carrying capacity and use marine waters for aquaculture utilities (internal shipping lanes, aquaculture facilities, etc.) in potential areas to be developed. Therefore, from the potential area obtained from this study, only a tiny portion can be used for aquaculture production and is referred to as the effective area [1-7, 29-34]. Effective area is the area of water that can be used for production activities.

The effective area for the development of marine aquaculture in the Sangihe Islands District is about 2,839.98 ha with commodities including seaweed, fish (grouper, yellowfish, ornamental fish), lobster shrimp, sea cucumbers, and others (Photo 34 up to 92).

Seaweeds

The potential location for developing seaweed cultivation is in the Sangihe Islands District, with 4,604.98 ha spread over the east and west coasts of Sangihe Island and the coast of small islands. The potential development of seaweed cultivation sites using a long line system with 25 × 25 m (625 m²/unit) can be developed as many as 44,208 units.

Estimated production can reach 38,681.81 tons per year. Utilization of this potential can involve the human resources of 5,525 families. Based on the average price of seaweed at the farmer level, it is around Rp. 7,500 per kg, then the potential production value is around IDR 290,113,572 million per year.

Floating Net Cage (FNC)

The effective potential for developing fish farming in the FNC is around 19.82 ha or about 8,863 bags of 3×3 m (9 m²/bag). The commodity being developed is grouper for export. The potential production is estimated at 576.09 tons per year with a production value of around IDR. 480.07 billion. 985 families can be involved in fish farming activities in this KJA, assuming 1 unit of FNC with six bags per unit.

Sea Cucumber

In the Sangihe Islands District, sea cucumber cultivation activities have been carried out in Talengen Bay using FCN (Floating Cage Net). The potential for the development of KJT in the coastal waters of the Sangihe Islands District is about 28.44 ha effective. The KJT construction used is 12 × 12 m² in size, so the number of KJT units that can be developed is around 1,975 units. One unit of KJT can produce about 1,077 kg/unit of sea cucumber per cycle. The commodities traded for sea cucumbers are dry commodities, so the potential production of dried sea cucumbers in the Sangihe Islands District is around 136.50 tons per year with a production value of around Rp. 51.188 billion. The absorption of labor in developing the sea cucumber cultivation area in KJT is around 988 families.

Pearl Cultivation

Pearl cultivation is one of the potentials developed in the Sangihe Islands District. The suitability analysis shows that the marine waters of the Sangihe Islands District have development potential. Pearl oyster cultivation in the Sangihe Islands District has not yet been carried out, so it requires an introduction from outside, namely through fishery investors. The area of potential pearl cultivation sites is about 34.2 ha, effective to develop the long line and raft method.

Fishery Port Development Support System

Dagho Port is a fishing port at CFP level (Coastal Fishery Port) covering an area of 4 hectares, which is located about 40 km south of Tahuna city. The current condition of Dagho Port is relatively not optimal because many facilities at the port are damaged. Its location, which is relatively far from urban areas, causes not many fishers to take advantage of the facilities in Dagho.

In the Spatial plans Guidance of the Sangihe Islands District itself, Dagho has been directed as a fishing port which in the future is expected to be developed into an Archipelago Fishery Port (AFP). When viewed from the land area and the characteristics of the surrounding waters, Dagho has excellent potential as a port that becomes a fishery center, including the fishery product processing industry.

The port of Santiago is an area planned for port development, where the current location is a vacant lot equipped with several warehouse buildings. The site boundary included in the development area is the northern side of Tatehe Street and directly adjacent to the Tax Office.

The land is a former Bina Marga Office with an area of about 1.1 ha, and there is a development plan to the west side of 0.9 ha so that the entire development will cover an area of 2 ha. There are buildings including offices, official residences, workshops, warehouses, and stone crusher areas in the area. The condition of the beach is relatively steep, and the waves are big, so handling is needed so that the port pool can function optimally. The site's location is

relatively strategic because it is close to the Tahuna urban area. The site has the potential to be developed as a maritime-based economic area. A coastal ring road that crosses the side of the port plan requires special handling related to circulation regulation.

Port System Handling Needs

Dagho Port

The need for handling the fishing port development plan, namely:

- a) The need for infrastructure development on the site to support fishery port activities at the level of AFP.
- b) The need to provide significant capacity cold storage, ice factories, air blast freezers, and ice warehouses
- c) The need for the provision of supporting facilities to increase the capacity and expertise of fishers.
- d) The need for the development of the fishing industry supports fishing ports.
- e) The need for the provision of facilities for ship repair and fishing equipment.
- f) The need for the provision of clean water and electricity facilities to operate facilities at fishing ports.

Santiago Port

The need for handling the fishing port development plan, namely:

- a) The condition of the waters around Santiago with big waves and steep sea depths needs to be considered in the area's design around the harbor pool.
- b) The site needs to construct a breakwater to anticipate the high waves around Santiago.
- c) The need for port development with a focus on the preparation and storage of fishery commodities for export needs and the development of secondary tourism supporting functions, namely culinary and selling processed seafood.
- d) It is urgent to support port facilities development related to fisherman capacity development.

CONCLUSIONS

The Development of Integrated Marine and Fisheries Areas (IDMFA) in the Sangihe Islands District is a regional-based marine and fishery development concept with an area management approach and system with the principles of integration, efficiency, quality, and high-quality acceleration. This concept is essential to develop the potential of an area so that its management is carried out following the national vision and mission. The two areas designated as Integrated Marine and Fisheries Development Areas for IDMFA development in the Sangihe Islands District are the Santiago and Dagho areas. This selection was based on the fisheries potential of the two regions and the vision made by the Sangihe Islands District, namely "to make the Sangihe Islands District the main source of marine power in North Sulawesi Province." This effort is reasonable when viewed from the fishery potential of the Sangihe Islands District, which is located in the Fishery Management Area (FMA 716), which has a

good status based on the analysis of the EAFM (ecosystem approach fisheries management) system.

References

- [1] Bashari, H., Fauzan, P. A. & Lionata, H. The Current Status of the Critically Endangered Caerulean Paradise-Flycatcher *Eutrichomyias Rowley* on Sangihe, North Sulawesi. *Kukila*, 19 (2016) 21-29
- [2] Biasane, A. N., Fauzi, A, Monintja, D. R., & Soedharma, D. (2011). Kebijakan Pengelolaan Pulau Kecil Perbatasan Berbasis Geopolitik, Daya Dukung Ekonomi dan Lingkungan (Kasus Pulau Pulau Kecil Perbatasan Kepulauan Sangihe, Sulawesi Utara). *Jurnal Teknologi Perikanan dan Kelautan*, 2(2), 21-40
- [3] The Environmental Lesson from the Indigenous Wisdom of Seke Fishing Practice in Sangihe Archipelago of Indonesia. Saxo Publish, Copenhagen Denmark, 1 (2020), 1-123. ISBN: 9788740427691
- [4] Cassels, S., Curran, S. R., & Kramer, R. Do Migrants Degrade Coastal Environments? Migration, natural resource extraction, and poverty in North Sulawesi, Indonesia. *Human Ecology*, 33 (3) (2005) 329-363
- [5] Wakiri, S., & Mantjoro, E. Traditional Marine Tenure in Indonesia: A Study in Sangihe Islands. *Bull. Kagoshima Pref. College*, 43 (1992) 1-23
- [6] Kepel, T. L., Ati, R. N. A., Rustam, A., Rahayu, Y. P., Kusumaningtyas, M. A., Daulat, A., Hutahaean, A. A. Cadangan Karbon Ekosistem Mangrove di Sulawesi Utara dan Implikasinya Pada Aksi Mitigasi Perubahan Iklim. *Jurnal Kelautan Nasional*, 14 (2) (2019) 87-94
- [7] Manoppo, L., Marsoedi, Muhammad, S., Berhimpon, S. Sedimentation Rate and Total Suspended Solid (TSS) In Melombo Area, Salurang Village, Sangihe Archipelagic District. *International Journal of Engineering Inventions*, 3 (7) (2014) 48-55.
- [8] Allen GR, Conservation hotspots of biodiversity and endemism for Indo-Pacific coral reef fishes. *Aquatic Conservation: Marine and Freshwater Ecosystems* 18 (5) (2008) 541-556
- [9] Hutomo M, Moosa MK, Indonesian Coastal and Marine Biodiversity: Present Status. *Indian Journal of Marine Sciences* 14(1) (2005) 88-97
- [10] F. X. Kusumartono, A. Rizal. An integrated assessment of vulnerability to water scarcity measurement in small islands of Indonesia. *World News of Natural Sciences* 24 (2019) 117-133
- [11] A Khan, A. Rizal, Lantun P. D., Izza M. A, Junianto, Dedi S, Wildan G, Anta M. N, Tim S. Gray, Aileen C. M, Nicholas V. C. P. Skipjack (*Katsuwonus pelamis*) tuna pole-and-line marketing supply chains in Indonesia: Case study in Pulau Bacan. *AACL Bioflux*, 12(2) (2019) 636-641

- [12] R. Permana, A. Rizal, & Hasan, Z. Plastic Consumption in Group of Teens and Young Adults from Pangandaran District, Indonesia: A Glimpse of Environmental Awareness among the Locals outside Big Cities. *Asian Journal of Advanced Research and Reports*, 12(2) (2020) 1-9. <https://doi.org/10.9734/ajarr/2020/v12i230282>
- [13] Kurniasih I, Nurhayati A, Dewanti LP, Rizal A, Marine Tourism Potential in Pangandaran Regency. *Jurnal Perikanan dan Kelautan*, 10 (1) (2020) 54-65
- [14] Muftiadi A, Developing Tourism Village and Its Potential in Pangandaran District. *Jurnal AdBispreneur* 2 (2) (2017) 117-124
- [15] Achmad Rizal. Implementation of Tourism Development Policies in Garut District, West Java Province, Indonesia. *The Institute of Biopaleogeography named under Charles R. Darwin* 5 (2021) 1-40
- [16] A. Rizal, Apriliani, I.M., Permana, R., Nurruhwati, I. Development and coastal environment change, will have a meeting point? Case study of coastal zone of west java province, Indonesia. *Geojournal of Tourism and Geosites*, 31(3), 2020, 1034-1042
- [17] Zulpikar F, Prasetyo DE, Shelvatis TV, Komara KK, Pramudawardhani M, Economic Valuation of Environmental Service-Based Tourism Object in Batu Karas Beach-Pangandaran Using the Travel Cost Method. *Journal of Regional and Rural Development Planning* 1 (1) (2017) 53-63
- [18] Putri AE, Khadijah ULS, & Novianti E, Community Empowerment in The Development of Mangrove Tourism in Batu Karas of Pangandaran, West Java. *GeoJournal of Tourism and Geosites*, 31 (3) (2020) 972-978. <https://doi.org/10.30892/gtg.31306-52>
- [19] A. Rizal, Apriliani, I.M., Permana, R. Social morphology of poverty in tourism area: A thick description study in parakansalak village of sukabumi, West Java, Indonesia, *Geojournal of Tourism and Geosites*, 34(1), 2021, 132-139
- [20] Lester, J. A., & Weeden, C. Stakeholders, the natural environment and the future of Caribbean cruise tourism. *International Journal of Tourism Research*, 6(1), (2004) 39-50
- [21] Lozano, R., Carpenter, A., & Huisinigh, D. A review of 'theories of the firm' and their contributions to corporate sustainability. *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 106, (2015) 430-442
- [22] Mainardes, E., Alves, H., & Raposo, M. Stakeholder theory: Issues to resolve. *Management Decision*, 49(2) (2011) 226-252
- [23] Mardiatno, D., Malawani, M. N., & Nisaa', R. M. The future tsunami risk potential as a consequence of building development in Pangandaran Region, West Java, Indonesia. *International Journal of Disaster Risk Reduction*, 46, (2020) 101523. [doi:10.1016/j.ijdr.2020.101523](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijdr.2020.101523)
- [24] Marsh, E. The effects of cruise ship tourism in coastal heritage cities. *Journal of Cultural Heritage Management and Sustainable Development*, 2(2) (2012) 190-199
- [25] Junianto, Iskandar, Achmad Rizal, and Windi Damayanti. The Influence of Concentration of Acetic Acid and Pepsin Enzyme in Nilem Fish Skin Collagen

- Extraction to the Amount of Rendement Produced. *World News of Natural Sciences*, 21 (2018) 164-170
- [26] H. Heryati, W. S. Pranowo, N. P. Purba, A. Rizal, L. P. Yuliadi. Java Sea Surface Temperature Variability during ENSO 1997–1998 and 2014–2015. *Omni-Akuatika* 14 (1) (2018) 384-396
- [27] Molina-Azorín, J. F., & Font, X. Mixed methods is sustainable tourism research: An analysis on prevalence, designs and application in JOST (2005-2014). *Journal of Sustainable Tourism*, 24(4) (2016) 549-573
- [28] Lemmetyinen, A., & Go, F. M. Building a brand identity in a network of cruise Baltic's destinations – a multi-authoring approach. *Journal of Brand Management*, 17 (7) (2010) 519-531
- [29] Leposa, N. Problematic blue growth: A thematic synthesis of social sustainability problems related to growth in the marine and coastal tourism. *Sustainability Science*, 15 (2020) 1233-1244
- [30] Moreno, A., & Amelung, B. Climate change and coastal & marine tourism: Review and analysis. *Journal of Coastal Research*, 56 (2009) 1140–1144
- [31] Morgan, D. L. Living within blurry boundaries: The value of distinguishing between qualitative and quantitative research. *Journal of Mixed Methods Research*, 12 (3) (2018) 268-279
- [32] Achmad Rizal. Implementation of Tourism Development Policies in Garut District, West Java Province, Indonesia. *The Institute of Biopaleogeography named under Charles R. Darwin* 5 (2021) 1-40
- [33] Achmad Rizal. Urgency of Coastal Resources Management Through Coastal Tourism in Wondama Bay District, West Papua Province, Indonesia. *The Institute of Biopaleogeography named under Charles R. Darwin* 8 (2021) 1-39
- [34] K. A. I. L. Wijewardena Gamalath. Beautiful, natural places and tourist attractions in Sri Lanka. *The Institute of Biopaleogeography named under Charles R. Darwin* 3 (2021) 1-44

Appendix

Photo 1. Sangihe Islands District in Indonesian Map

Photo 2

Photo 3

Photo 4

Photo 5

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Photo 8

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